

Simplified Charts- for Easy Daily Reporting of Bacterial Antibiotic Sensitivity Test

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Abstract

Introduction: Quality microbiological, antimicrobial sensitivity reporting (AST) is helpful to prescribe appropriate antibiotic and ultimately beneficial to curb down antimicrobial resistance. Even the resulting antibiogram is crucial in monitoring antimicrobial resistance (AMR) and the basis for formulation of antibiotic policy. Microbiology laboratories follow CLSI & EUCAST guidelines which are vast & exhaustive. Further, these guidelines are frequently updated with few changes. To follow these guidelines in daily microbiological reporting especially at heavily burdened laboratories may have chances of error in AST reporting by missing few points. To evaluate the overall AST pattern for minimizing errors, improvement in adherence to guidelines and also to maintain uniformity in AST reporting, we need handy tool for daily reporting of AST and easy referral.

Material & Methods: Concise tables were prepared for present study using recent CLSI 2024 guidelines & few points from EUCAST guidelines. Tables for Disc diffusion test & MIC values were prepared for ready reference, this will be useful for daily routine Reporting of AST for all commonly encountered pathogens. For easy understanding, codes in the form of symbols, colors & abbreviations were described.

Results: For present study, results were discussed as per charts & tables (applied for copyright) & following points were highlighted. The charts with tables are prepared for *Enterobacteriales spp.*, *Nonfermenters spp.*, *Staphylococcus spp.*, *Enterococcus spp.*, *Streptococcus spp.*, *Haemophilus spp.* & *Neisseria species*. The following AST points are included in the Tables - Disc diffusion & MIC breakpoints, Tier wise cascade reporting, Intrinsic resistance, Intermediate zone/SDD zone, lack of disc diffusion guidelines for different drug-bug combination, Marking of page numbers for quick and easy reference, Equivalent/surrogate agent for routine AST workup, Antibiotics not useful in CSF & urine samples.

Conclusion: This study depicts easy instructions & referral of guidelines which can be edited as per different laboratory practices. The quality AST reporting & antibiogram are helpful to strengthen antibiotic stewardship which is also highlighted in recent NMC guidelines for hospital-based colleges & ICMR at National level healthcare practices

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Introduction

Background- Quality microbiological, antimicrobial sensitivity reporting (AST) is helpful to prescribe appropriate antibiotic and ultimately beneficial to curb down antimicrobial resistance. Even the

resulting antibiogram is crucial in monitoring antimicrobial resistance (AMR) and the basis for formulation of antibiotic policy. Microbiology laboratories follow CLSI & EUCAST guidelines

which are vast & elaborative. Further, these guidelines are frequently updated with few changes. To follow these guidelines in daily microbiological reporting especially at heavily burdened laboratories may have chances of error in AST reporting by missing few points. Few soft wares are available for AST reporting where only zone size or MIC need to feed but prior to upload correct analyzation/evaluation of reports is necessary. To evaluate the overall AST pattern for minimizing errors, improvement in adherence to guidelines and also to maintain uniformity in AST reporting, we need handy tool for daily reporting of AST and easy referral.

Here we present concise Tables prepared by primarily referring recent CLSI 2024 guidelines & few points were added from EUCAST 2024 guidelines. Tables depict both disc diffusion & MIC values of majorly encountered Gram positive & Gram negative pathogens and multidrug resistant 'ESKAPE' group of organisms (superbugs) targeted in National action plan against AMR. Maximum comments have been imbibed in these charts.

General codes in the form of symbols, colours along with abbreviations are described in general instructions (Table 1 & 2). Tables are prepared for both disc diffusion & MIC of Enterobacterales (Table 3 & 4), Nonfermenters - *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Acinetobacter* spp., *Burkholderia cepacia*, *Stenotrophomonas maltophilia* (Table 5 & 6), Gram positive organisms - *Staphylococcus* spp., *Enterococcus* spp. (Table 7 & 8), *Streptococcus pneumoniae*, *Streptococcus* spp. β hemolytic group and viridans group (Table 9 & 10) and other Gram negative organisms - *Haemophilus influenzae*, *Haemophilus parainfluenzae*, *Neisseria gonorrhoeae*, *Neisseria Meningitidis* (Table 11 & 12).

The following AST points are included in the Tables -

- Both Disc diffusion (Manual /conventional) & MIC (Automated) breakpoints
- Color coded Tier wise cascade reporting
- List of organisms- with Intrinsic resistance to different antibiotics
- Highlighted- intermediate zone/SDD zone for different antibiotics
- Highlighted- disc diffusion guidelines for different drug-bug combination
- Tables are marked with page numbers for quick and easy reference, wherever further detailed reading of guidelines is required
- Additional information in terms of equivalent agent, surrogate agent
- Antibiotics not useful in CSF & urine samples have also been symbolized.

General page and the Table of the particular organism need to be repeatedly referred simultaneously to decode the meaning of symbols & abbreviations.

Eg. 1) *Proteus vulgaris* isolate in urine sample – As per institutional policy, tier wise antibiotics can be added in AST reporting with simultaneous checking of zone size/MIC values.

Intrinsic resistance check is added. So, the user will easily remember to add comment about intrinsic resistance for Ampicillin, 1st generation Cephalosporins, Tetracyclines, Tigecyclines, Nitrofurantoin, Polymyxin & Colistin or report them resistant.

SDD zone check for Piperacillin- tazobactam and Cefepime is indicated with blue color code.

E.g. 2) *Staphylococcus saprophyticus* isolated in urine sample-

Azithromycin, Erythromycin, Clindamycin, Minocycline, Lefamulin, Chloramphenicol not to be reported from urine sample is indicated with symbol *.

For methicillin resistance check, information is provided that Cefoxitin disc can be used as surrogate agent to oxacillin (indicated with OX-CX) & apply zone size of OX-CX (Other).

Eg. 3) *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* isolated in pus sample- (Manual/ Conventional)

Amikacin as written in urine group- will not be added in AST (Indicated with symbol-U).

For ceftazidime-avibactam intermediate zone should not be written (indicated with Blue color code).

Colistin, Polymyxin B should not to be reported in disc diffusion testing as guidelines are not available (indicated with grey color code)

These Tables can be edited according to the different laboratory practices. Revision of guidelines will be possible during yearly updating of charts. Concise guidelines in Tables for specific drug- bug combination with color pattern & other symbol use makes visual impression. Above mentioned points (Intrinsic resistance, tier system....) can easily refer at the time of reporting. Easy referral saves time and avoid chances of missing points. Comments also can be added in AST report with the help of charts.

The introduction of such tools in day-to-day practice will be beneficial to eliminate the errors, strengthen the quality of the AST reporting and can generate accurate, uniform antibiogram. This will be one step in ensuring better patient outcomes & strengthen our fight against AMR.

General instructions page

Abbreviations, Colour codes & Symbols- (Table 1)

CODE	Referred for
Green	Tier 1
Yellow	Tier 2
Orange	Tier 3
Red	Tier 4
Blue-	Regarding intermediate zone (No intermediate zone/ SDD)
Grey	No disc diffusion guidelines/No MIC guidelines
Purple	Difference in CLSI & EUCAST (other than zone size)
(C-Page No)	Refer CLSI
(E-Page no)	Refer EUCAST
©	Testing drug (Equivalent agent/surrogate agent/Deduced to ..)
U-	Urine only
U-E	for E. coli Urinary tract isolates only
U-U	Uncomplicated UTI
*	Not to be tested for urine sample
#	Not to be tested for CSF sample
¥	Not to be reported in respiratory sample

Abbreviations (Table 2)

P	Penicillin	IMP	Imipenem	COT	Cotrimoxazole
PI	Piperacillin	ETP	Ertapenem	Azi	Azithromycin
TI	Ticarcillin	MRP	Meropenem	E	Erythromycin
TCC	Ticarcillin- clavulanic acid	DOR	Doripenem	CD	Clindamycin
AMP	Ampicillin	IMP-REL	Imipenem- Relebactam	TE	Tetracycline
AMC	Amoxicillin-clavulanic acid	MRP-VABOR	Maropenem- vaborbatum	DOX	Doxycycline
AMP-SUL	Ampicillin- Sulbactam	GEN	Gentamicin	MIN	Minocycline
PIT	Piperacillin-Tazobactam	AK	Amikacin	CIP	Ciprofloxacin
CAZ-AVI	Ceftazidime - avibactam	TOB	Tobramycin	NX	Norfloxacin
CEFTA-TAZO	Ceftalazone- tazobactam	NET	Netilmicin	LOM	Lomefloxacin
DAPTO	Daptomycin	HLG	High level Gentamicin	LE	Levofloxacin
LZ	Linezolid	HLS	High Level Streptomycin	OF	Ofloxacin
VA	Vancomycin	CL	Colistin	NA	Nalidixic acid
Quin- Dalfo	Quinipristin-Dalfopristin	PB	Polymyxin-B	NIT	Nitrofurantoin
DALBA	Dalbamicin	AZT	Aztreonam	FOS	Fosfomycin
ORITA	Oritamicin	TELA	Telamycin		

Enterobacterales (Disc diffusion) (CLSI 2024)(Table 3)					
	Antibiotics	S	I/SDD	R	Comments
Tier 1	AMP [®] (U-U)	≥17	14-16	≤13	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> All gram-ve are IR to Macrolides, Glycopeptides, Clindamycin & Linezolid. E. coli- No IR to B lactum K. pneumoniae- IR-Ampicillin, Ticarcillin K. aerogenes- -IR-Ampicillin, Amoxy-clav, AMP-SUL, Cepha-I, Cephamycin, Cepha-II (Cefuroxime) (pg-318) Citrobacter freundii- -IR-Ampicillin, Amoxy-clav, AMP-SUL, Cepha-I, Cephamycin, Cepha-II (Cefuroxime) (pg-318) Citrobacter Koseri-A-IR-MP, Piperacillin, Ticarcillin Enterobacter Cloacae-IR- AMP, AMC, AMP-SUL(pg-318) Proteus mirabilis -IR-Tetracycline, Tigecycline, Nitrofurantoin, Polymyxin, Colistin, No IR to B lactum Proteus vulgaris- -IR-AMP, Cepha-I, Tetracycline, Tigecycline, NIT, Polymyxin, Colistin Providencia (Stuartii & rettgeri) -IR- – Ampicillin, Amoxy-clav, Cepha-I, Tetracycline, Tigecycline, Nitrofurantoin, Polymyxin, Colistin Serratia Marscens--IR- AMP, AMC, AMP-SUL, Cepha-I, Cephamycin, Cephalosporins-II, Nitrofurantoin, Polymyxin, Colistin Yersinia -IR-AMP, AMC, Ticarcillin, Cephalosporins-I Salmonella & Shigella-IR-1st & 2nd generation Cephalosporins, Cephamycins
	Cefazolin (C-pg 61)# [®]	≥23	20-22	≤19	
	Cefotaxime [®] or	≥26	23-25	≤22	
	Ceftriaxone [®] (E-pg 15)	≥23	20-22	≤19	
	AMC (E-pg 14) (U-U)	≥18	14-17	≤13	
	AMP- SUL	≥15	12-14	≤11	
	PIT	≥25	21-24 (SDD)	≤20	
	GEN (C-pg 65)	≥18	15-17	≤14	
	CIP (E-pg 16)#	≥26	22-25	≤21	
	LE#	≥21	17-20	≤16	
COT	≥16	11-15	≤10		
CIP (Salm & Shigella)	≥31	21-30	≤20		
LE (Salm. & Shigella)	-	-	-		
Tier 2	Cefuroxime (Oral)#	≥23	15-22	≤14	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ESBL- R- All Penicillin, 1,2,3,4th Cephalosporins, Monobactam S- Carbapenem, BL+ BLI AmpC- R- All cephalosporins(Except- 4th gen), B lacum+ B lactum inhibitor S- 4th gen cephalosporins, Carbapenems
	Cefuroxime (Parenteral)#	≥18	15-17	≤14	
	Cefepime(C-pg 62)	≥25	19-24 (SDD)	≤18	
	ETP#	≥22	19-21	≤18	
	IMP (E-pg 16)#	≥23	20-22	≤19	
	MRP (E-pg 16)	≥23	20-22	≤19	
	TOB (C-pg 65)	≥17	13-16	≤12	
	AK (C-pg 65)	≥20	17-19	≤16	
	Cefotetan#	≥16	13-15	≤12	
	Cefoxitin#	≥18	15-17	≤14	
TE#	≥15	12-14	≤11		
Tier 3	Cefiderocol				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> © Testing Drug Ampicillin Pefloxacin (Salmonella) Cefazolin Cefotaxime/ Ceftriaxone Viceversa Colistin/ Polymyxin B viceversa
	CAZ- AVI	≥21		≤20	
	IMP- REL (C-Pg-60)	≥25	21-24	≤20	
	MRP- VABOR (C-Pg-60)	≥18	15-17	≤14	
	Plazomicin	≥18	15-17	≤14	
Tier 4	Aztreonam	≥21	18-20	≤17	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> For Salmonella-Shigella (C-pg—70) ETP,IMP,MRP,TE (Tier 4) Fecal- AMP, Fluroquinolones, COT Extraintestinal- AMP, Fluroquinolones, COT + 3rd gen Cephalosporins, Chloramphenicol
	Ceftaroline	≥23	20-22	≤19	
	Ceftazidime	≥21	18-20	≤17	
	CEFTA- TAZO	≥22	19-21	≤18	
U	Cefazolin (U-U) [®]	≥15		≤14	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Amoxicillin Ciprofloxacin Cefdinir, Cefpodoxime, Cefuroxime
	NIT	≥17	15-16	≤14	
	FOS (U-E) (C-pg 67)	≥16	13-15	≤12	
	NA	≥19	14-18	≤13	
	NX#	≥17	13-16	≤12	
O T H E R	PI				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> For Salmonella-Shigella (C-pg—70) ETP,IMP,MRP,TE (Tier 4) Fecal- AMP, Fluroquinolones, COT Extraintestinal- AMP, Fluroquinolones, COT + 3rd gen Cephalosporins, Chloramphenicol
	DOR#	≥23	20-22	≤19	
	Mecillinam (U-E)	≥15	12-14	≤11	
	TCC	≥20	15-19	≤14	
	Cefoperazone	≥21	16-20	≤15	
	Ceftizoxime	≥25	22-24	≤21	
	CL& PB (C-pg 65) [®]				
	NET	≥15	13-14	≤12	
	Azi (Salm typhi)*	≥13		≤12	
	Azi (Shigella)*	≥16	11-15	≤10	
	LOM#	≥22	19-21	≤18	
	DOX	≥14	11-13	≤10	
Chloramphenicol*	≥18	13-17	≤12		

Enterobacterales (MIC) (CLSI 2024)(Table 4)					
	Antibiotics	S	I/SDD	R	Comments
Tier 1	AMP© (U-U)	≤8	16	≥32	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> All gram-ve are IR to Macrolides, Glycopeptides, Clindamycin & Linezolid. E.coli- No IR to B lactum K. pneumoniae- IR-Ampicillin, Ticarcillin K. aerogenes- -IR-Ampicillin, Amoxy-clav, AMP-SUL, Cepha-I, Cephamycin, Cepha-II (Cefuroxime) Citrobacter freundii- -IR-Ampicillin, Amoxy-clav, AMP-SUL, Cepha-I, Cephamycin, Cepha-II (Cefuroxime) Citrobacter Koseri-A-IR-MP, Piperacillin, Ticarcillin Enterobacter Cloacae-IR- AMP, AMC, AMP-SUL Proteus mirabilis -IR-Tetracycline, Tigecycline, Nitrofurantoin, Polymyxin, Colistin, No IR to B lactum Proteus vulgaris- -IR-AMP, Cepha-I, Tetracycline, Tigecycline, NIT, Polymyxin, Colistin Providencia (Stuartii & rettgerii) -IR- – Ampicillin, Amoxy-clav, Cepha-I, Tetracycline, Tigecycline, Nitrofurantoin, Polymyxin, Colistin Serratia Marscens--IR- AMP, AMC, AMP-SUL, Cepha-I, Cephamycin, Cephalosporins-II, Nitrofurantoin, Polymyxin, Colistin Yersinia- -IR-AMP, AMC, Ticarcillin, Cephalosporins-I
	Cefazolin (C-pg 61) #	≤2	4	≥8	
	Cefotaxime© #or	≤1	2	≥4	
	Ceftriaxone © (E-pg 15)	≤1	2	≥4	
	AMC (E-pg 14)(U-U)	≤8/4	16/8	≥32/16	
	AMP- SUL	≤8/4	16/8	≥32/16	
	PIT	≤8/4	16/4(SDD)	≥32/4	
	GEN (C-pg 65)	≤2	4	≥8	
	CIP (E-pg 16)	≤0.25	0.5	≥1	
	LE#	≤0.5	1	≥2	
	COT	≤2/38		≥4/76	
CIP(Salm & Shigella)	≤0.06	0.12-0.5	≥1		
LE (Salm. & Shigella)	≤0.12	0.25-1	≥2		
Tier 2	Cefuroxime (Oral) #	≤4	8-16	≥32	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ESBL- R- All Penicillin, 1,2,3,4th Cephalosporins, Monobactam S- Carbapenem, BL+ BLI AmpC- R- All cephalosporins(Except- 4th gen), B lacum+ B lactum inhibitor S- 4th gen cephalosporins Carbapenems
	Cefuroxime (Parenteral)	≤8	16	≥32	
	Cefepime(C-pg 62)	≤2	4-8 (SDD)	≥16	
	ETP	≤0.5	1	≥2	
	IMP (E-pg 16)	≤1	2	≥4	
	MRP (E-pg 16)	≤1	2	≥4	
	TOB (C-pg 65)	≤2	4	≥8	
	AK (C-pg 65)	≤4	8	≥16	
	Cefotetan#	≤16	32	≥64	
	Cefoxitin#	≤8	16	≥32	
	TE#	≤4	8	≥16	
Tier 3	Cefiderocol	≤4	8	≥16	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> © Testing Drug Ampicillin Pefloxacin (Salmonella) Cefazolin Cefotaxime/ Ceftriaxone Viceversa Colistin/ Polymyxin B viceversa
	CAZ- AVI	≤8/4		≥16/4	
	IMP- REL (C- Pg-60)	≤1/4	2/4	≥4/4	
	MRP- VABOR (C- Pg-60)	≤4/8	8/8	≥16/8	
	Plazomicin	≤2	4	≥8	
Tier 4	Aztreonam	≤4	8	≥16	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> For Salmonella-Shigella (C-pg—70) ETP,IMP,MRP,TE (Tier 4) Fecal- AMP, Fluroquinolones, COT Extraintestinal- AMP, Fluroquinolones, COT + 3rd gen Cephalosporins, Chloramphenicol
	Ceftaroline	≤0.5	1	≥2	
	Ceftazidime	≤4	8	≥16	
	CEFTA- TAZO	≤2/4	4/4	≥8/4	
U	Cefazolin(U-U) ©	≤16		≥32	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> © Testing Drug Ampicillin Pefloxacin (Salmonella) Cefazolin Cefotaxime/ Ceftriaxone Viceversa Colistin/ Polymyxin B viceversa
	NIT	≤32	64	≥128	
	FOS (U-E)(C-pg 67)	≤64	128	≥256	
	NA	≤16		≥32	
	NX#	≤4	8	≥16	
O T H E R	PI	≤8	16	≥32	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> © Testing Drug Ampicillin Pefloxacin (Salmonella) Cefazolin Cefotaxime/ Ceftriaxone Viceversa Colistin/ Polymyxin B viceversa
	DOR#	≤1	2	≥4	
	Mecillinam (U-E)	≤8	16	≥32	
	TCC	≤16/2	32/2-64/2	≥128/2	
	Cefoperazone	≤16	32	≥64	
	Ceftizoxime	≤1	2	≥4	
	CL & PB(C-pg 65) ©		≤2	≥4	
	NET	≤8	16	≥32	
	Azi (Salm typhi)	≤16		≥32	
	Azi (Shigella)	≤8	16	≥32	
	LOM#	≤2	4	≥8	
	DOX	≤4	8	≥16	
Chloramphenicol*	≤8	16	≥32		

Pseudomonas (disc diffusion) aeruginosa					CLSI 2024 (Table 5)	Acinetobacter (disc diffusion)				
		S	I	R			S	I	R	
T i e r 1	Ceftazidime	≥18	15-17	≤14	Pseudomonas aeruginosa- IR- AMP, Amox, AMP-SUL, AMC, Cefotaxime, Ceftriaxone, ETP, TE, Tigecycline, COT, C	T i e r 1	AMP-SUL	≥15	12-14	≤11
	Cefepime	≥18	15-17	≤14			Ceftazidime	≥18	15-17	≤14
	PIT	≥22	18-21	≤17			Cefepime	≥18	15-17	≤14
	TOB (E-pg-22)	≥19	13-18	≤12			CIP#	≥21	16-20	≤15
	CIP#	≥25	19-24	≤18			LE#	≥17	14-16	≤13
2	LE#	≥22	15-21	≤14	Acineto baumanii/ Acineto calcoaceticus – IR - AMP, Amox, AMC, AZM, ETP, TE, C, Trimethoprim	T i e r 2	GEN (E-pg-29)	≥15	13-14	≤12
	IMP	≥19	16-18	≤15			TOB (E-pg-29)	≥15	13-14	≤12
T i e r 3	MRP (E-pg-21)	≥19	16-18	≤15	Burkholderia cepacia- IR- (pg-320) AMP, Amox, PI, TI, AMP-SUL, AMC, ETP, POLY-B, CL	3	IMP	≥22	19-21	≤18
	Cefiderocol (C-pg-76)	≥18	13-17	≤12			MRP (E-pg-28)	≥18	15-17	≤14
	CAZ-AVM	≥21		≤20			AK (E-pg-29)	≥17	15-16	≤14
	CEFT-TAZO	≥21	17-20	≤16			PIT	≥21	18-20	≤17
4	IMP-REL	≥23	20-22	≤19	Stenotrophomonas maltophilia- IR- (pg-320) AMP, Amox, PI, TI, PIT, Cefotaxime, Ceftriaxone, AZT, IMP, MRP, Aminoglycosides, AMP-SUL, AMC, ETP, POLY-B, CL, FOS, Trimethoprim	4	COT	≥16	11-15	≤10
	AZT	≥22	16-21	≤15			MIN	≥16	13-15	≤12
U	AK-U-(E-pg-22)	≥17	15-16	≤14	CLSI- Pseudomonas aeruginosa & other Pseudomonas spp. (Nonenterobacterales) have different guidelines	U	TE	≥15	12-14	≤11
	PI	≥22	18-21	≤17			Stenotrophomonas maltophilia (Disc diffusion)	DOX	≥13	10-12
O T H E R	NET	≥15	13-14	≤12	EUCAST- Pseudomonas aeruginosa & other Pseudomonas spp. Have same guidelines.	O T H E R		Cefotaxime	≥23	15-22
	OF#	≥16	13-15	≤12			Ceftriaxone	≥21	14-20	≤13
U	TCC	≥24	16-23	≤15	CL & PB (C-pg-83)	U	CL & PB (C-pg-83)			
	DOR	≥19	16-18	≤15			TE	≥15	12-14	≤11
O T H E R	LOM- U	≥22	19-21	≤18	Stenotrophomonas maltophilia (disc diffusion)	O T H E R	Piperacillin	≥21	18-20	≤17
	NX- U	≥17	13-16	≤12			TCC	≥20	15-19	≤14
U	CL,PB (C-pg 77)				Chloramphenicol* - - -	U	DOR	≥18	15-17	≤14
							Netilmicin			
1	Ceftazidime				Chloramphenicol* - - -	1	Cefiderocol	≥15		
	MRP						Chloramphenicol*	-	-	-
	MIN						TCC	-	-	-
	LE	-	-	-						
	COT									

Pseudomonas (MIC) aeruginosa					CLSI 2024 (Table 6)	Acinetobacter (MIC)					
		S	I	R			S	I	R		
T l e r 1	Ceftazidime	≤8	16	≥32	Pseudomonas aeruginosa- IR- AMP, Amox, AMP-SUL, AMC, Cefotaxime, Ceftriaxone, ETP, TE, Tigecycline, COT, C	T l e r 1	AMP-SUL	≤8/4	16/8	≥32/16	
	Cefepime	≤8	16	≥32			Ceftazidime	≤8	16	≥32	
	PIT	≤16/4	32/4	≥64/4			Cefepime	≤8	16	≥32	
	TOB (E-pg-22)	≤1	2	≥4			CIP#	≤1	2	≥4	
	CIP#	≤0.5	1	≥2			LE#	≤2	4	≥8	
	LE#	≤1	2	≥4	GEN (E-pg-29)	≤4	8	≥16			
						TOB (E-pg-29)	≤4	8	≥16		
2	IMP	≤2	4	≥8	Acinetobacter baumannii/ Acinetobacter calcoaceticus – IR - AMP, Amox, AMC, AZM, ETP, TE, C, Trimethoprim	T l e r 2	IMP	≤2	4	≥8	
	MRP(E-pg-21)	≤2	4	≥8			MRP (E-pg-28)	≤2	4	≥8	
T l e r 3	Cefiderocol	≤4	8	≥16			AK (E-pg-29)	≤16	32	≥64	
	CAZ-AVM	≤8/4		≥16/4			PIT	≤16/4	32/4-64/4	≥128/4	
	CEFT-TAZO	≤4/4	8/4	≥16/4			COT	≤2/38		≥4/76	
	IMP-REL	≤2/4	4/4	≥8/4	MIN	≤4	8	≥16			
4	AZT	≤8	16	≥32	Burkholderia cepacia- IR- (pg-286) AMP, Amox, PI, TI, AMP- SUL, AMC, ETP, POLY-B, CL	3	Cefiderocol (C-pg-82)	≤4	8	≥16	
							Sulbactam- Durlobactam	≤4/4	8/4	≥16/4	
							4	DOX	≤4	8	≥16
							Cefotaxime	≤8	16-32	≥64	
							Ceftriaxone	≤8	16-32	≥64	
U	AK(E-pg-22)	≤16	32	≥64	Stenotrophomonas maltophilia- IR- (pg- 320) AMP, Amox, PI, TI, PIT, Cefotaxime, Ceftriaxone, AZT, IMP, MRP, Aminoglycosides, AMP-SUL, AMC, ETP, POLY-B, CL, FOS, Trimethoprim	CL,PB (C-pg- 83)		≤2	≥4		
O T H E R	PI	≤16	32	≥64							
	NET	≤8	16	≥32							
	OF	≤2	4	≥8							
	TCC	≤16/2	32/2- 64/2	≥128/2							
	DOR	≤2	4	≥8							
	LOM (U)	≤2	4	≥8							
	NX (U)	≤4	8	≥16							
	CL,PB(C-pg 77)		≤2	≥4	U	TE	≤4	8	≥16		
Burkholderia Cepacia (MIC)					CLSI- Pseudomonas aeruginosa & other Pseudomonas spp. (Nonenterobacteriales) have different guidelines EUCAST- Pseudomonas aeruginosa & other Pseudomonas spp. Have same guidelines	O T H E R	Stenotrophomonas maltophilia (MIC)				
	Ceftazidime	≤8	16	≥32				LE	≤2	4	≥8
	MRP	≤4	8	≥16				MI	≤1	2	48
	MIN	≤4	8	≥16				COT	≤2/38		≥4/76
	LE	≤2	4	≥8							
	COT	≤2/38		≥4/76				Cefiderocol	≤1		
	C*	≤8	16-	≥32							
	TCC	≤16/2	32/2- 64/2	≥128/2				C*	≤8	16-	≥32
								TCC	≤16/2	32/2-64/2	≥128/2

CLSI 2024 - Disc Diffusion – Table 7									
Staphylococcus				Enterococcus					
	S	I	R		S	I	R		
T I E R 1	AZI* [⊙]	≥18	14-17	≤13	T	AMP (C-P-107)	≥17		≤16
	E* [⊙] #	≥23	14-22	≤13	1	P (C-P-107)	≥15		≤14
	CD*#	≥21	15-20	≤14					
	OX (aureus & lugdu)(C-pg-99)					VA	≥17	15-16	≤14
	OX(epidermidis, pseudo & Schei)	≥18		≤17	T	HLG			
	OX-CX(aureus&lugdu)(C-pg-100)	≥22		≤21	2	DAPTO¥			
	OX-CX(epidermidis)(C-pg-100)	≥25		≤24		LZ	≥23	21-22	≤20
	OX-CX(other)(C-pg-100)	≥25		≤24					
	DOX	≥16	13-15	≤12	T	HLS (C-pg-107,222)			
	MIN*	≥19	15-18	≤14	3	Tedizolid (E.faecalis)			
TE#	≥19	15-18	≤14						
COT-	≥16	11-15	≤10		DALBA (C-pg-108)				
VA (aureus+ other)				T	ORITA (C-pg-108)				
				4	TELA (C-pg-108)				
T	P	≥29		≤28					
2	DAPTO¥				U	NIT	≥17	15-16	≤14
	LZ	≥26	23-25	≤22		CIP#	≥21	16-20	≤15
						LE#	≥17	14-16	≤13
	Ceftaroline (aureus)	≥25	20-24	≤19		FOS (C-pg-110)	≥16	13-15	≤12
T	Tedizolid(C-pg-104) (S.aureus)	19	16-18	15		TE#	≥19	15-18	≤14
3	RIF	≥20	17-19	≤16					
	Lefamulin*#	≥23			O	NX-U	≥17	13-16	≤12
					T	Teicoplanin	≥14	11-13	≤10
	CIP#/ OR	≥21	16-20	≤15	H	E#*	≥23	14-22	≤3
T	LE#/OR	≥19	16-18	≤15	E	DOX	≥16	13-15	≤12
4	MOX#	≥24	21-23	≤20	R	MIN	≥19	15-18	≤14
	DALBA/ORITA/TELA(S.aureus)					RIF	≥20	17-19	≤16
	GEN	≥15	13-14	≤12		C*	≥18	13-17	≤12
						Quin-Dalfo (C-p110)	≥19	16-18	≤15
U	NIT	≥17	15-16	≤14	Enterococcus- IR - Aminoglycosides (Except high level) Cephalosporins, CD, COT				
	NX	≥17	13-16	≤12					
	Sulfomethaxazole	≥17	13-16	≤12	All gram positive, Organism- IR - Aztreonam, CL, PB				
	Trimethoprim	≥16	11-15	≤10					
O	Teicoplanin				Enterococci- If Penicillin (s)- Predict to AMP, AMX, AMC, AMP-SUL, PIT, Enterococci- If AMP(s)- Predict to AMC, AMP-SUL, PIT				
T	Dirithromycin	≥19	16-18	≤15					
H	LOM#	≥22	19-21	≤18					
E	OF#	≥18	15-17	≤14					
R	C*	≥18	13-17	≤12					
	Quin-Dalfo(C-pg-104)	≥19	16-18	≤15					

OX-CX- Resistant- MRSA/MRCONS – Resistant to all Penicillins, Cephalosporins, carbapenems (Except-ceftaroline)

OX-Disc- Not for S. aureus & lugdu
CX- Disc- MIC Not for S. pseudo S. schleiferi

Erythromycin (S)- Predict to, Azithromycin(S), Clarithromycin(S)
 If Levofloxacin(S)- Predict to, Gemifloxacin(S), Moxifloxacin(S)
 If Tetracycline(S)- Predict to, Doxycycline(S), Minocycline(S)
 If Linezolid (S)- Predict to, Tedizolid (S)

		CLSI 2024 - MIC – Table 8							
Staphylococcus		S	I	R	Enterococcus		S	I	R
T I E R 1	AZI* [©]	≤2	4	≥8	T	AMP(C-Pg-107)	≤8		≥16
	E#* [©]	≤0.5	1-4	≥8	1	P(C-Pg-107)	≤8		≥16
	CD#*	≤0.5	1-2	≥4					
	OX(aureus&lugdu)(C-p99)	≤2		≥4		VA	≤4	8-16	≥32
	OX(epidermidis, pseudo & Schei)(C-pg-100)	≤0.5		≥1	T	HLG			
	OX-CX (aureus&lugdu)(C-pg-100)	≤4		≥8	2	DAPTO(faecium) ¥		4(SDD)	≥8
	OX-CX(epidermidis)					DAPTO(Other) ¥	≤2	4	≥8
	OX-CX(other)	≤0.5		≥1		LZ	≤2	4	≥8
	DOX	≤4	8	≥16					
	MIN*	≤4	8	≥16	T	HLS(C-pg-107,222)			
	TE#	≤4	8	≥16	3	Tedizolid (E.faecalis)	≤0.5		
	COT	≤2/38		≥4/76					
	VA((aureus)	≤2	4-8	≥16	T	DALBA(C-pg-108)	≤0.25		
	VA(other)	≤4	8-16	≥32	4	ORITA(C-pg-108)	≤0.12		
	T	P	≤0.12		≥0.25		TELA(C-pg-108)	≤0.25	
2	DAPTO¥	≤1							
	LZ	≤4		≥8	U	NIT	≤32	64	≥128
						CIP#	≤1	2	≥4
						LE#	≤2	4	≥8
T	Ceftaroline (aureus)	≤1	2-4	≥8		FOS(p-110)	≤64	128	≥256
3	Tedizolid(C-104) (aureus)	≤0.5	1	≥2		TE#	≤4	8	≥16
	RIF	≤1	2	≥4					
	LEFA#*	≤0.25							
					O T H E R	NX (U)	≤4	8	≥16
T	CIP#/ OR	≤1	2	≥4		Teico	≤8	16	≥32
4	LE#/ OR	≤1	2	≥4		E#*	≤0.5	1-4	≥8
	MOX#	≤0.5	1	≥2		DOX	≤4	8	≥16
	DALBA(aureus)	≤0.25				MIN	≤4	8	≥16
	ORITA&TELA (aureus)	≤0.12				RIF	≤1	2	≥4
	GEN	≤4	8	≥16		C*	≤8	16	≥32
						Quin-Dalfo (p110)	≤1	2	≥4
U	NIT	≤32	64	≥128					
	NX	≤4	8	≥16					
	Sulfo	≤256		≥512					
	Trimetho	≤8		≥16					
O	Teicoplanin	≤8	16	≥32					
T	Dirithro	≤2	4	≥8					
H	LOM#	≤2	4	≥8					
E	OF#	≤1	2	≥4					
R	C*	≤8	16	≥32					
	Quin-Dalfo(C-pg-104)	≤1	2	≥4					

OX-CX- Resistant- MRSA/MRCONS – Resistant to all Penicillins, Cephalosporins, carbapenems (Except-ceftaroline)

OX-Disc- Not for S. aureus & lugdu
CX- Disc- MIC Not for S. psedo S. schleiferi

Erythromycin (S)- Predict to, Azithromycin(S), Clarithromycin(S)
 If Levofloxacin(S)- Predict to, Gemifloxacin(S), Moxifloxacin(S)
 If Tetracycline(S)- Predict to, Doxycycline(S), Minocycline(S)
 If Linezolid (S)- Predict to, Tedizolid (S)

CLSI 2024 - Disc Diffusion - Table 9

CLSI 2024 - Disc Diffusion - Table 9									
	Strepto(Pneumo)	S	I	R		Strepto(B hemo)	S	I	R
T I E R 1	E*#	≥21	16-20	≤15		CD	≥19	16-18	≤15
	P(OX)	≥20			T	E	≥21	16-20	≤15
	P(NONMEN)				!	P/	≥24		
	P(MEN)					AMP	≥24		
	P(ORAL) #					TE#	≥23	19-22	≤18
	COT	≥19	16-18	≤15	T	CTX	≥24		
	CTX/ CTR (MEN)				3	CTR	≥24		
	CTX/ CTR (NONMEN)				VA	≥17			
	MRP					CPM	≥24		
T I E R	CD	≥19	16-18	≤15	T	CEFTAROLINE	≥26		
	DOX/	≥28	25-27	≤24	I	LZ	≥21		
	TE#	≥28	25-27	≤24	E	TEDI			
	LE#	≥17	14-16	≤13	R	DAPTO			
	MOX#	≥18	15-17	≤14	4	LE#	≥17	14-16	≤13
	VA	≥17				DALBA/ ORITA			
	AMOX(NONMEN)					TELA			
T I E R 4	AMC(NONMEN)				O	DOR			
	CPM (MEN)p-125				T	MRP			
	CPM(NONMEN)				H	ETP			
	CEFTAROLINE (NONMEN)	≥26			E	AZI#	≥18	14-17	≤13
	ETP				R	CLARITHRO#	≥21	17-20	≤16
	IMP				C	C	≥21	18-20	≤17
	LEFA#	≥19				Quino-Dalfo	≥19	16-18	≤15
	LZ	≥21							
	CXM (Parent)					STREPTO (VIRI)	S	I	R
	CXM (Oral) #					AMP			
RIF	≥19	17-18	≤16	T	P				
				1	CTX	≥28	26-27	≤25	
O	Cefaclor#				CTR	≥27	25-26	≤24	
T	Cefpodoxime								
H	DOR#				VA	≥17			
E	AZI*	≥18	14-17	≤13					
R	Clarithro*	≥21	17-20	≤16		LZ	≥21		
	C*	≥21		≤20	T	TEDI			
	Quino-Dalfo	≥19	16-18	≤15	3	DALBA/ ORITA			
						TELA			
						CPM	≥24	22-23	≤21
					T	CEFT-TAZ			
					4	CD	≥19	16-18	≤15
						E#	≥21	16-20	≤15
						LE#	≥17	14-16	≤13
						DAPTO			
						AZI#	≥18	14-17	≤13
						CLARITHRO	≥21	17-20	≤16
						TE#	≥23	19-22	≤18
						C	≥21	18-20	≤17
						Quino-Dalfo	≥19	16-18	≤15
						ETP#			
						MRP			
						DOR#			

© Testing Drug	Predict to
Erythro	Azithro, Clarithro
LE (S)	Gemiflox, Moxiflox (S)
TE (S)	Doxy, Mino
LZ (S)	Tedizolid

CLSI 2024 - MIC - Table 10

Strepto(Pneumo)					Strepto(B hemo)						
	S	I	R		S	I	R		S	I	R
T	E	≤0.25	0.5	≥1	T	CD	≤0.25	0.5	≥1		
I	P(OX)				1	E	≤0.25	0.5	≥1		
E	P(NONMEN)	≤2	4	≥8		P/	≤0.12				
R	P(MEN)	≤0.06		≥0.12		AMP	≤0.25				
1	P(ORAL)	≤0.06	0.12-1	≥2							
	COT	≤0.5/9.5	1/19-2/38	≥4/76		TE#	≤2	4	≥8		
	CTX/CTR(MEN)	≤0.5	1	≥2	T	CTX/	≤0.5				
	CTX/ CTR (NONMEN)	≤1	2	≥4	3	CTR	≤0.5				
						VA	≤1				
	MRP	≤0.25	0.5	≥1							
T	CD	≤0.25	0.5	≥1	T	CPM	≤0.5				
I	DOX/	≤0.25	0.5	≥1	I	CEFTAROLINE	≤0.5				
E	TE#	≤1	2	≥4	E	LZ	≤2				
R	LE#	≤2	4	≥8	R	TEDI	≤0.5				
	MOX#	≤1	2	≥4	4	DAPTO	≤1				
	VA	≤1				LE#	≤2	4	≥8		
						DALBA/ORITA	≤0.25				
T	AMOX(NONMEN)	≤2	4	≥8	O	TELA	≤0.12				
I	AMC(NONMEN)	≤2/1	4/2	≥8/4	T	DOR	≤0.12				
E	CPM (MEN)	≤0.5	1	≥2	H	MRP	≤0.5				
R	CPM(NONMEN)	≤1	2	≥4		ETP#	≤1				
4	CEFTAROLINE (NONMEN)	≤0.5			E	AZI#	≤0.5	1	≥2		
	ETP#	≤1	2	≥4	R	CLARITHRO#	≤0.25	0.5	≥1		
	IMP#	≤0.12	0.25-0.5	≥1		C	≤4	8	≥16		
	LEFA#	≤0.5				Quino-Dalfo	≤1	2	≥4		
	LZ	≤2									
	CXM (Parente)	≤0.5	1	≥2		STREPTO(VIRI)					
	CXM (Oral) #	≤1	2	≥4	T	AMP	≤0.25	0.5-4	≥8		
	RIF	≤1	2	≥4		P	≤0.12	0.25-2	≥4		
O	Cefaclor#	≤1	2	≥4	1	CTX	≤1	2	≥4		
T	Cefpodoxime	≤0.5	1	≥2		CTR	≤1	2	≥4		
H	DOR#	≤1		≥		VA	≤1				
E	AZI#	≤0.5	1	≥2		LZ	≤2				
R	Clarithro#	≤0.25	0.5	≥1	T	TEDI	≤0.25				
	C	≤4		≥8	3	DALBA/ ORITA	≤0.25				
	Quino-Dalfo	≤1	2	≥4		TELA	≤0.06				
						CPM	≤1	2	≥4		
					T	CEFT-TAZ	≤8/4	16/4	≥32/4		
					4	CD#	≤0.25	0.5	≥1		
						E#	≤0.25	0.5	≥1		
						LE#	≤2	4	≥8		
						DAPTO	≤1				
						AZI#	≤0.5	1	≥2		
						CLARITHRO#	≤0.25	0.5	≥1		
						TE#	≤2	4	≥8		
						C	≤4	8	≥16		
						Quino-Dalfo	≤1	2	≥4		
						ETP/ DOR#	≤1				
						MRP	≤0.5				
						DOR#					

© Testing Drug	Predict to
Erythro	Azithro, Clarithro
LE (S)	Gemiflox, Moxiflox (S)
TE (S)	Doxy, Mino
LZ (S)	Tedizolid

CLSI 2024- MIC - Table -12									
Hemophilus influenzae & Para					Neisseria gonorrhoeae				
		S	I	R		S	I	R	
1	AMP (C-p-114)	≤1	2	≥4	T	AZI	≤1		
	Cefotaxime/ OR	≤2			I	Ceftriaxone	≤0.25		
T	Ceftriaxone/ OR	≤2			E	Cefixime	≤0.25		
I	Ceftazidime	≤2			R	Ciprofloxacin	≤0.06	0.12-0.5	≥1
E	AMC	≤2/1	4/2	≥8/4	1	Tetracycline	≤0.25	0.5-1	≥2
R	AMP-SUL	≤2/1		≥4/2	O	P (C-Pg-119)	≤0.06	0.12-1	≥2
	CIP#/ MOX# /	≤1			T	CX	≤2	4	≥8
2	LE#	≤2			H	CPM	≤0.5		
	COT	≤0.5/9.5	1/19-2/38	≥4/76	E	Cefotaxime	≤0.5		
	MRP	≤0.5			R	Cefpodoxime	≤0.5		
	ERT/	≤0.5				Spectinomycin	≤32	64	≥128
T	IMP	≤4							
I	AZI	≤4							
E	Cefaclor	≤8	16	≥32					
R	Cefixime#	≤1							
	CEFT-TAZ (C-p-114)	≤0.5/4							
4	Cefuroxime#	≤4	8	≥16					
	Ceftaroline	≤0.5							
	Rifampin	≤1	2	≥4					
	TE#	≤2	4	≥8					
	PIT	≤1/4		≥2/4					
	AZT	≤2							
	DOR	≤1							
	C	≤2	4	≥8					
<p>H. influenzae- CSF – Only AMP, 3rd gen. Cephalosporins (Ceftizoxime, Cefotaxime, Ceftriaxone, Ceftazidime), Chloramphenicol, MRP to report</p> <p>H. influenzae- Respiratory sample –often not necessary AST testing for AMC, AZI, Cefaclor, Cefdinir, Cefixime, Cefpodoxime, Cefuroxime, Clarithromycin</p> <p>Only for H. influenzae to report- Ceftaroline, Lefamulin, Ceftalazone- tazobactam</p> <p>Rifampin- Prophylaxis of case contact</p>					<p>Neisseria Meningitidis</p> <p>T Penicillin ≤0.06 0.12-0.25 ≥0.5</p> <p>1 Cefotaxime/ ≤0.12</p> <p>Ceftriaxone ≤0.12</p> <p></p>				
					<p>T Meropenem ≤0.25</p> <p>I Azithromycin ≤2</p> <p>E Ciprofloxacin ≤0.03 0.06 ≥0.12</p> <p>R Levofloxacin ≤0.03 0.06 ≥0.12</p> <p>Minocycline ≤2</p> <p>4 COT ≤0.12/2.4 0.25/4.75 ≥0.5/9.5</p> <p>Rifampin ≤0.5 1 ≥2</p> <p></p>				
					<p>Ampicillin ≤0.12 0.25-1 ≥2</p> <p></p>				
					<p>Azithromycin, Minocycline, Ciprofloxacin, Rifampin- Only for prophylaxis of case contacts for N. gonorrhoeae.</p> <p>Do Not apply breakpoints to therapy of patient with invasive meningococcal disease</p>				

Disclaimer-These charts do not replace CLSI/EUCAST as a referral guideline

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References

1. CLSI 2024. Performance Standards for Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing. 34th edition. CLSI supplement M100. Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute, Wayne, PA.
2. The European Committee on Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing. Breakpoint tables for interpretation of MICs and zone diameters. Version 14.0, 2024. <http://www.eucast.org>.